

5-Phenylazo Salicylaldehyde Complexes of Transition Metals as Potential Semiconductors

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The D. C. conductivities of solid metal complexes of transition metal ions Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II), Mn(II) with phenylazo salicylaldehydes in their pellet form are reported. It is found that semiconducting behaviour is observed only when the complexes get pyrolysed in the range ~310 to 340°K.

SEMICONDUCTION of complexes of metals or compounds of metals has gained sufficient ground in recent years. Some work on the semiconducting properties of rare earth complexes of Fluorescein¹ was reported from these laboratories. Fielding² have investigated some complexes for their semiconducting properties and has come to the conclusion that complexes containing metal atom in different oxidation states in crystallographically equivalent positions are capable of acting as semiconductors. Infact, the experiments concluded by this worker showed $\text{Fe}_4[(\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6)]_3$ as an intrinsic semiconductor. Ksendzov and Strongova³ have shown an interconnection of electrical conductivity with exchange interaction of ions and electrons in 3d shells. Even in compounds of the type CoFe_2O_4 , semiconducting properties have been discovered⁴. Unusual high value of conduction, explained on quantum mechanical tunnel model, was proposed by Kwan and Zwickel⁵ in the case of tris(*o*-phenanthroline) Fe(II) hexachloro-iridate and its analogs withdipyridyl. Intrinsic semiconduction was observed by some workers⁶ in the case of transition metal complexes of 6-mercaptapurine and 4-mercapto-6, 7-diphenylpteridine. Since delocalised electrons and conjugation impart semiconducting properties to compounds, the present worker thought that the metal complexes of *p*-phenylazo salicylaldehydes, having azo-dye as one of the constituents, may well serve as potential semiconductors.

Experimental

The complexes were prepared as reported earlier⁷⁻⁹. The D.C. conductivity of the complexes were determined in their pellet form using Elico Million Megohmmeter model R.M. 70 R. The instrument could read and measure upto 10^{14} ohms and the test voltage varied from 100 to 500 volts; the accuracy being at the lower range $\pm 5\%$. The pellet of the test sample was put in a typical cell fabricated in this laboratory and resistance in

Megohms was calculated using the expression.

$$\text{Resistance in Megohms} = \frac{\text{Meter reading} \times \text{Multiplied factor}}{\text{Applied voltage}}$$

Multiplied factor being 10, 10^2 , 10^3 , etc., in the present investigation.

The sample was heated in a tubular furnace in which D. C. conductivity cell snugly fitted, the temperature of the furnace being increased by steps from room temperature to about 200° and regulated by using Dimmerstat and Sunvic dial.

The slope values obtained from $\log \zeta$ vs $1/T$ were converted to E_a values in eV by using expression :

$$\text{Slope (-ve)} = E_a / 2.303 \times 0.864 \times 10^{-4}$$

It is to be noted that resistivities (σ) of these samples were obtained only after subjecting them to several temperature increase, temperature-drop cycles.

During the D. C. conductivity measurements several errors crop in. Grain boundaries are developed during compression, metallic particles of the die may get adhered to during pelletisation or there may be an imperfect contact of the electrodes to the pellet due to slight deformation during pellet formation. The present worker applied several compression cycles before taking the final results of the conductivity measurements and only limiting values were chosen as standard. The metallic particles, possibly adhered to the pellet, were gently removed by scrapping the pellet with stainless steel blade so as to not disturb the physical dimensions of it. The pellet was smeared with silver paint to ensure a good contact with the electrodes. Care was also taken not to apply very high voltages to avoid any leakages across the border. Results of D. C. conductivities given in Table 1 are only for those samples which gave satisfactory reproducibility.

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TABLE 1—SOME TYPICAL VALUES OF $\log \sigma$ FOR THE 5-PHENYLAZO SALICYLALDEHYDE COMPLEXES OF TRANSITION METALS. FIRST COLUMN UNDER THE COMPLEX GIVES TEMPERATURE ($^{\circ}\text{K}$) AND THE SECOND ONE $\log \sigma - 12$ AND THOSE MARKED WITH ASTERISK $\log \sigma - 9$

Mn(II)- <i>o</i> -TAS		Ni(II)- <i>m</i> -TAS	
312.5	1.54	315.45	1.72
416.6	2.10	431.03	2.10
Mn(II)- <i>m</i> -Cl-PAS		Ni(II)- <i>p</i> -TAS	
312.5	0.98	299.40	2.40
416.6	1.18	384.61	2.48
Mn(II)- <i>p</i> -TAS		Ni(II)- <i>o</i> -Cl-PAS	
303.03	1.34	317.46	1.00
416.06	1.60	432.90	1.28
Mn(II)- <i>p</i> -Cl-PAS		Ni(II)- <i>m</i> -Cl-PAS	
312.5	1.09	283.28	1.58
416.6	1.60	322.58	2.60
Mn(II)- <i>m</i> -TAS		Ni(II)- <i>p</i> -Cl-PAS	
312.5	0.28	285.70	2.28
434.78	0.38	322.58	2.60
Co(II)- <i>p</i> -TAS		Cu(II)- <i>m</i> -TAS	
294.11	1.22	333.33	0.80*
341.29	1.12	400.00	0.88*
Co(II)- <i>o</i> -Cl-PAS		Cu(II)- <i>o</i> -TAS	
303.03	0.80	291.54	1.20*
411.52	1.60	416.66	0.76*
Co(II)-PAS		Cu(II)-PAS	
312.50	1.09	312.50	1.46*
416.66	1.52	400.00	2.20*
Co(II)- <i>m</i> -Cl-PAS			
322.50	1.46		
416.66	1.56		
Co(II)- <i>o</i> -TAS			
317.46	0.46		
413.22	0.58		
Cu(II)- <i>p</i> -Cl-PAS			
303.03	1.59		
370.30	1.98		
Cu(II)- <i>p</i> -TAS			
341.29	0.80		
431.03	0.92		

Results and Discussion

The resistance values of the pellets of the salts ranging from \sim room temperature (27°) to 180° were converted into conductivity values (σ) by taking into account the thickness of the pellet and its diameter and evaluating thickness/area parameter of the pellet of a particular salt. Generally the diameter of the pellet remained constant (~ 1.307 cm) since the same die was used and the thickness varied from 0.228 to 0.287 cm according to the amount of sample pressed. The results of the D. C. conductivities are presented here in the form of plots of $\log \sigma - 12$ vs $1000/T$ as the range of conductivities was found to be 10^{-10} to $10^{-14} \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$. It will be seen from the plots (Figs. 1a and 1b), where for the sake of brevity only one typical plot (Fig. 1a, b for Cu(II) salts has been given) that there is a consistent fall of conductivity as the temperature rises roughly from room temperature $\sim 300^{\circ}\text{K}$ to $\sim 350^{\circ}\text{K}$ and later on there is a rise in conductivity with a rise of temperature showing a definite semiconduction.

The initial trend is a typical of metallic conduction⁴ where conductivity (σ) decreases as temperature rises while the latter part of behaviour is a characteristic of semiconduction. Bhohe and his

FIG 1(a)
 ○ Cu(II) Complex of *o*-Tas
 △ Cu(II) Complex of *m*-Tas
 □ Cu(II) Complex of *p*-Tas
 ◇ Cu(II) Complex of Pas

FIG 1(b)
 ○ Cu(II) Complex of *o*-Chloropas
 △ Cu(II) Complex of *m*-Chloropas
 □ Cu(II) Complex of *p*-Chloropas

collaborator^{1,7-9} have found that the typical values of E_a from the relation $\log \zeta = \log \zeta_0 + E_a/kT$ ranging from 0.2 to 0.7 eV fall in the category of semiconduction. It was also observed that there was no change in the composition of the complex in the range of $\sim 300^{\circ}\text{K}$ to 350°K and C, H, N and M analyses of the samples kept at 300° , 363° and 480°K shows little variation ($\text{C} \pm 0.18\%$, $\text{H} \pm 0.3\%$, $\text{N} \pm 0.5\%$), but the substance got an internal conversion due to pyrolysis though not positively suggested by the analyses. The products were analysed at each stage of the temperature and the composition was found to be intact. The initial analysis (300°K) of the complexes when they were subjected to resistance measurements are summarised as :

The C, H, N and M analyses of the complexes as found are Cu(II)-PAS 62.20, 4.00, 10.24, 12.44 ; *o*-Cl-PAS, 54.40 3.21, 10.26, 10.84 ; *m*-Cl-PAS,

53.45, 2.25, 9.68; 10.00, *-p*-Cl-PAS 52.85, 2.88, 10.00, 10.79; *-o*-TAS, 58.29, 5.28, 10.42, 10.79; *-p*-TAS 63.00, 4.50, 10.82, 11.42; Ni(II) *-o*-Cl-PAS 50.58, 3.22, 9.10, 10.20; *-m*-Cl-PAS 54.56, 3.10, 9.55, 9.78; *-p*-Cl-PAS 51.10, 3.20, 9.30, 9.53; *-m*-TAS 62.40, 4.00, 10.40, 11.07; *p*-TAS 58.42, 4.50, 9.77, 10.37; Co(II)-PAS 58.40, 5.00, 10.02, 58.02; *-o*-Cl-PAS 51.18, 3.40, 9.64, 9.48; *-m*-Cl-PAS 51.05, 4.18, 9.52, 9.35; *o*-TAS 58.40, 5.00, 9.80, 10.63; *-p*-TAS 58.74, 4.81, 9.65, 10.00; Mn(II) *-m*-Cl-PAS 52.60, 4.26, -, 9.50; *-p*-Cl-PAS 51.78, 3.65, -, 9.44; *o*-TAS 62.45, 4.50, -, 9.35; *-m*-TAS 60.18, 4.18, -, 9.45; *-p*-TAS 60.20, 4.60, -, 10.25. These analyses agree very well with those calculated.

TABLE 2—ENERGY GAP VALUES (=E_a) OF COMPLEXES OF 5-PHENYLAZO SALICYLALDEHYDES

Complexes	E _a , eV
Cu(II) :	
PAS	0.765
<i>o</i> -chloro-PAS	0.303
<i>m</i> -chloro-PAS	0.436
<i>p</i> -chloro-PAS	0.638
<i>o</i> -TAS	0.153
<i>m</i> -TAS	0.327, 0.547
<i>p</i> -TAS	0.114
Ni(II) :	
<i>o</i> -chloro-PAS	0.452, 0.818
<i>m</i> -chloro-PAS	0.227
<i>p</i> -chloro-PAS	0.781
<i>m</i> -TAS	0.887
<i>p</i> -TAS	0.182, 0.179
Co(II) :	
PAS	0.332
<i>o</i> -chloro-PAS	0.301
<i>m</i> -chloro-PAS	0.398
<i>o</i> -TAS	0.153
<i>p</i> -TAS	0.746
Mn(II) :	
<i>m</i> -chloro-PAS	0.159
<i>p</i> -chloro-PAS	0.211
<i>o</i> -TAS	0.162
<i>m</i> -TAS	0.313
<i>p</i> -TAS	0.265

PAS=Phenylazo salicylaldehyde.
TAS=Toluene azo salicylaldehyde.

It will be observed from the E_a values given in Table 2, that these values generally increase in the complexes of chloro substituted PAS from ortho to para as E_a (*o*-Cl-PAS), E_a (*m*-Cl-PAS) < E_a (*p*-Cl-PAS). This case seems to be favourable for delocalised electrons. In general, chlorosubstituted complexes show greater E_a values than methyl substituted ones.

The nature of conduction (*n* or *p* type) in the complexes investigated could not be established because of lack of instrumentation for measuring Hall-Coefficients and the difficulty in getting the complexes as well-defined crystals.

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References

1. R. A. BHOBE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, **51**, 846.
2. P. E. FIELDING, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1954, **22**, 1153.
3. Ya. M. KSENDZOV and V. A. STRONGOVA, *Proc. Intern. Conf. Semicond. Phys.*, Prague, 1960, **92**.
4. G. H. JONKER, *Phys. and Chem. Solids*, 1959, **9**, 165.
5. S. C. KWAN and A. M. ZWICKEL, *U. S. Dept. Comm. Office Tech. Service A. D.* 1963, **7**, 296; 1965, **62**, 7706.
6. S. CHATTERJEE, A. K. GHOSE and ABROHOMSOHIS, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **44**, 183.
7. K. G. DESHMUKH and R. A. BHOBE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **54**, 375.
8. K. G. DESHMUKH and R. A. BHOBE, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1978, **49**, 135.
9. K. G. DESHMUKH and R. A. BHOBE, *Curr. Sci.*, 1977, **46**, 67.